

Teacher's Expectations for the Era Pandemic Covid 19

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ABSTRACT: In this discussion, the focus is on a teacher. Why? Because most people learn from a teacher, so it is necessary to be an example and idol by everyone. The example intended a good example for every student, both from his actions or his words. Not only that, a teacher also deserves idolism because he is an example, not because he is an artist, or model, but because he is able to become a teacher who is expected and able to be a positive energy for students. However, what is often seen is that some teachers are completely indifferent to what is required and obliged, so it becomes a problem for the portrait of a teacher in the future. Students become successful, not only because of themselves, their parents, their environment, but also in a very supportive school environment, namely the teacher. Then it needs to be understood that a teacher is indeed very influential.

KEYWORDS: Teacher; Problem; Expectation

1. INTRODUCTION

The world of education is very much discussed by the wider community, from any perspective. This is related a student and an educator. Because in the learning process, it must be understood these educators and students their respective roles and tasks. A teacher who gives an explanation or lesson and students who receive an explanation or lesson, then the expected learning process is created. However, it should be understood that not everything is going well, both in terms of students or even from the teacher himself.

In this discussion, the focus is on a teacher. Why? Because most people learn from a teacher, so it is necessary to be an example and idol by everyone. The example intended a good example for every student, both from his actions or his words. Not only that, a teacher also deserves idolism because he is an example, not because he is an artist, or model, but because he is able to become a teacher who is expected and able to be a positive energy for students.

The educators who become the best future are able to understand the situation of students in many problem by providing solutions that can help, are able to manage classes properly, and have competencies and basic skills in teaching. However, what is often seen is that some teachers are completely indifferent to what is required and obliged, so it becomes a problem for the portrait of a teacher in the future. Students become successful, not only because of themselves, their parents, their environment, but also in a very supportive school environment, namely the teacher. Then it needs to be understood that a teacher is indeed very influential. So, it's necessary for the writer to explain about how the figure of teacher hopes for the future.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of Education and Teacher

2.1.1. Definition of Education

Education is a human effort to "humanize humans". Humans are essentially God's creatures of the highest degree compared to other creatures. His creation is due to having the ability to speak and rasio, so that humans are able to develop themselves as civilized humans (Nana Sudjana, 2005). Education is one of the efforts in advancing the quality of the nation, including Indonesia. Until now, education has been embedded and still trusted as a medium for building intelligence (Syarifuddin Nurdin, 2005). Improvement of smart, skilled, independent, and noble human resources continues to be pursued through the education process.

Seeing the two meanings explained, it can be understood that how important education for everyone. Through education, someone will figure out a lot of things that may not previously been obtained, which is why one of the things that are important to education is educating the nation and improve the quality of people, especially Indonesia.

The learning process is an educator's activity as a subject matter, and students as recipients of the lesson. In the process, for both are actively causing interaction and communication that harmony for the achievement of learning objectives. (Syarifuddin

Teacher's Expectations for the Era Pandemic Covid 19

However, the mistake made by a teacher is that sometimes giving praise only to diligent student who are considered, will be different from not-active students. That is because the teacher seems to only give praise to those he likes and does not give praise to those who are considered negative.

3.3. Using “Destructive Discipline”

For this purpose, the teacher must direct what is good, and be an example, patient, and understanding (E. Mulyasa, 2017). Destructive discipline is something that teachers need to pay attention when giving assignments, for example. So, what must be understood is that whatever the teacher gives to the students, later they have to give feedback or give the punishment to accordance with what is their fault.

3.4. Ignoring Student Differences

The teacher should be able to identify the individual differences of students, and determine the general characteristics. In this case, the teacher must understand the characteristics of students that must be developed and which must be redirected (E. Mulyasa, 2017). Student differences are something that is perfectly natural, but that is not natural when a teacher never wants to understand about these differences, both differences in intelligence, biological, psychological, learning styles, and others.

3.5. Feel the Smartest

If this really happens, then the teacher must be democratic to be willing to learn again, the teacher must be a lifelong learner who always adjusts his knowledge to the developments. If not, it will miss the train and be an orthodox teacher (E. Mulyasa, 2017). Feeling your smartest is something you should avoid, let alone being a teacher. Sometimes something unexpected from students and can be used as a lesson for a teacher. So, of course that teachers should not feel the smartest of the students they teach.

3.6. Unfair (Discriminative)

Efforts that can be made to avoid this include by saving “feelings” until the loved students complete their education program, of course must be sincere and do not be afraid of people taking it (E. Mulyasa, 2017). In the world of education, a teacher not allowed to discriminate students in providing an assessment. If it is supposed to get less value, then give the appropriate value.

3.7. Forcing Students

Intend to become a teacher as worship. Wake up, “Oh my teacher, so that your name is always in my heart.” (Muzakkir, 2012). Sometimes, the factor could make the low profession teacher recognition explained by Sudjana in Usman, because:

1. The view of anyone can be a teacher as long as knowledgeable, be a teacher is easy.
2. The force areas, provides opportunities for someone who does not have the expertise to become a teacher.
3. Many teachers do not appreciate their profession (Moh. Uzer Usman, 2017).

Some of the teacher portraits described earlier are things that sometimes become obstacles to seeing a portrait of a teacher in the future. Why? Because what is supposed to be owned and controlled by a teacher is not in accordance with what should be. However, not all teachers are like that, there are also teachers who do have competence who are the hope of the future.

3.8. Teacher's Expectations In the Future

In the process of achieving the goal of education, it is necessary for teachers who are creative and fun. This is important, especially in each lesson, teachers have a central role, both as planners, implementers, and evaluators of learning (Abd. Rahman Getteng, 2011).

A teacher is expected for the future, not a teacher who only carry out their duties free of charge or not with a sincere heart, not just sharing the subject material, but make happy learners during progress.

Teachers who can understand the difficulties of students in terms of learning and other difficulties outside the problem of learning, then a teacher will be liked by their students (Syaiful Bahri Djamarah, 2014). For that reason, one thing that must be understood by a teacher is be a person who always makes it easy for students on problems that might occur in a good way, not by making it easy. Because a teacher becomes an example for students and students are imitators.

As an example, a teacher must have a personality that can be used as a profile and an idol, his whole life is a perfect figure. That is the impression of the teacher as an ideal figure. Few teachers do that which are not good, will reduce their \ charisma gradually dissolves from identity. For this reason, personality is a very sensitive matter, like proverb is “blunt outside, pointed inside.” (Syaiful Bahri Djamarah, 2014). Being a teacher must be really men guard the good name of the teacher as a whole, because sometimes we hear that only one teacher who behaves badly, but the blame or highlighted there was a teacher as a whole, although not behave badly.

Commenting on the poor quality of education is an indication of the need for a professional teacher. For this reason, a teacher is expected not only to run his profession, but a teacher must have a strong interest to carry out their duties in accordance with the rules of teacher professionalism required. Teachers in the era of information and communication technology are not just teaching, they must be learning managers. This implies that each teacher is expected to be able to create learning conditions that

Teacher's Expectations for the Era Pandemic Covid 19

challenge the creativity and activities of students, motivate students, use multimedia, multi-method, and multi-source in order to achieve the learning objectives as expected (Rusman, 2012). This is the portrait of the professional teacher you should be.

The quality personality of the teacher is very important because this is professional responsibility as well as being the core of professional strength and readiness to always develop them selves. (Syarifuddin Nurdin, 2005) The quality of a teacher can be viewed in two terms, in terms of the process and results. From the process, the teacher is said to be successful if he is able to involve most students actively, both are physically, mentally, and socially in learning. In addition, it can be seen in terms of the passion and enthusiasm of teaching, and the presence of self-confidence. Whereas in terms of results, the teacher is said to be successful if that the learning provided is able to change the behavior of most educators better mastery of basic competencies (Abd. Rahman Getteng, 2011).

In implementing the various policies above, teachers are required to become good disseminators of information. The teachers are also as a planner (designer), implementer, and evaluator of learning. If learning is directed to meet the personal needs of students by providing the knowledge and training the skills they need, there must be a dependence on effective and organized standard material. For this reason, new roles are needed from the teachers, they are required to have technical skills that make it possible to organize the material and manage it in the learning and formation of student competencies (Abd. Rahman Getteng, 2011).

The teacher becomes a good sample for all parents and the community in educating their children while in school, become a very instrumental in delivering the children at all levels of success, either to live in the local community and the global world.

The idolized teacher will only be born from a teacher who has the qualities that are implied by Allah. In his word, QS al-Muddassir74: 1-7.

يٰۤاَيُّهَا الْمُدَّثِّرُ ﴿١﴾ قُمْ فَأَنْذِرْ ﴿٢﴾ وَرَبِّكَ فَكَبِّرْ ﴿٣﴾ وَتَيَّابِكَ فَطَهِّرْ ﴿٤﴾ وَالرُّجْزِ ﴿٥﴾
فَآهْجُرْ ﴿٦﴾ وَلَا تَمُنْ بِتَسْكِينِكُمْ ﴿٧﴾ وَلِرَبِّكَ فَاصْبِرْ ﴿٨﴾

Translation:

- 1) O people who are cheering. 2) Get up and give a warning! 3) Your Lord exalts! 4) Clean your clothes, 5) and sin, leave!
- 6) Don't give (with the intention of) getting more (in return). 5) To fulfill the commandments of your Lord, be patient.

In addition, the teacher who takes the child who was illiterate became literate the person who was stupid became smart, the person who was originally in the dark, became bright and so on. A teacher will always be consistent in carrying out his mission and strive to put the teaching profession back to the respectable and dignified position, change the old paradigm and replace it with a new paradigm in viewing the teaching profession. This change in perspective must start with the teachers themselves, then social (Abd. Rahman Getteng, 2011).

A teacher's profession becomes very sensitive when discussed. Once doing worse, it will be in the spotlight. The portrait of future teachers will be a challenge for a teacher to always do something good and avoid things that can harm themselves, as well as harming the professional code of ethics that they carry. When you dare to make the decision to become a teacher that is expected in the future, then prepare a teacher to be responsible for the profession.

4. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

Conclusion

From the discussion that has been many things are actually done by teachers to be able to educate people being or students he teaches in order to become successful and able to boast. The portrait of future teachers will be a challenge for a teacher always do something good and avoid things that can harm themselves, as well as harming the professional code of ethics that they carry. When you dare to make the decision become a teacher that is expected in the future, then prepare a teacher to be responsible for the profession.

Implication

The hope of future teachers should be a basic concept in the world of Islamic education, especially a reference for academics who want to become a teacher. In the atmosphere of modernization, ideal teachers are demanded to be able to give an active generations who are ready to used.

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Teacher's Expectations for the Era Pandemic Covid 19

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